

Service Gap analysis in the light of Southern Railways

R. SHUNMUGASELVI, Fulltime Ph.D Research scholar, PG & Research Department of Commerce, Rani Anna Government College for Women, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli,

Dr.V.DARLINGSELVI, Assistant Professor of Commerce, Rani Anna Government College for Women,

Abstract

Indian Railways is the largest railway network in Asia. Oliver (1997) argues that service quality can be described as the result from customer comparisons between their expectations about the service they will use and their perceptions about the service company. The main objective of the study is to analyse the gap between passengers expectations and perceptions. Primary data were collected by interviewing **100** passengers of Rail transport in Southern Railway with a specially prepared interview schedule. The data were analysed by using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) software package. The researcher has applied Simple Percentage analysis, Gap analysis, Factor analysis and Correlation analysis. The result shows that the Gap analysis is positive in all the dimensions in general and is prominent in the dimensions of reliability and comfort.

Keywords: Expectation, Gap, Passengers, Perception, Satisfaction, Service Quality,

Introduction

Indian Railways (IR) is a statutory body under the ownership of Ministry of Railways, Government of India that operates India's national railway system. It manages the fourth largest national railway system in the world. The history of Indian Railways dates back to over 160 years ago. On 16th April 1853, the first passenger train ran between Bori Bunder (Bombay) and Thane, a distance of 34 km. It was operated by three locomotives, named Sahib, Sultan and Sindh, and had thirteen carriages railways virtually form the life-line of the Country, catering to its needs for large scale movement of traffic, both freight and passenger, thereby contributing to economic growth and also promoting national integration. In fact, railways constitute the backbone of surface transport system in India. (<https://artsandculture.google.com>). This study

aimstobringout thegapanalysisoftheservicequality ofSouthern railwaysfromtheviewpoint of 100 respondents from Tirunelveli District.

Southern Railway:TheSouthernRailwayhavingtheheadquarteredatChennai,isoneofthe 18 zones of Indian Railways. It is the earliest of the 18 zones of the Indian Railways created in independent India. It was created on 14 April 1951 by merging three state railways, namely, the Madras and Southern Mahratta Railway, the South Indian Railway Company, and the Mysore State Railway. Southern Railway has its headquarters in Chennai and has the following six divisions such as Chennai railway division, Tiruchirappalli railway division, Madurai railway division, Palakkad railway division, Salem railway division and Trivandrum railway division. **(Southern Railway Wikipedia)**

ServiceQuality:Gibson (2005) put forward that satisfied customers are likely to become loyal customers and that means that they are also likely to spread positive word of mouth. Understanding which factors that influence customer satisfaction makes it easier to design and deliver service offers that corresponds to the market demands. **Philip Kotler (1997)** defined service as ‘an action or an activity which can be offered by a party to another party, which is basically intangible and can not affect anyownership. Service may berelated to tangible product or intangible product’

DimensionsofServiceQuality:SERVQUAL Model

According to **A. Parasuraman, V.A.Zeithaml, and L.L.Berry**, it is during the service delivery that the quality of services is assessed and the contact with each customer implies as a chance to satisfy or dissatisfy the customer, a moment of truth. They defined customer satisfaction with regards to service as ‘by comparing perceptions of service received with expectations of service desired. In addition, **Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (PZB’s1988)** introduced five dimensions which led to the development of SETVQUAL, these dimensions are **tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy.**

TheSERVQUALInstrument

The **SERVQUAL** instrument developed by **Parasuraman (1991)** has proved popular, being used in many studies of service quality. **Parasuraman (1985)** developed the gap model and the subsequent **SERVQUAL** instrument designed to identify and measure the gaps between customers' expectations and perceptions of the service received. Service quality from the consumer's perspective depends on the direction and degree of difference between the expected service and the perceived service. Thus by comparing customer's expected service with customer's perceived service, hotels, for example can determine whether its service standard is appropriate. The gap between expectations and perceptions of performance determines the level of service quality from a customer's perspective. The **SERVQUAL** Instrument measures the five dimensions of Service Quality. These five dimensions are

Reliability: The ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately, **Assurance:** The knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence, **Tangibility:** The appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials, **Empathy:** The provision of caring, individualized attention to customer, **Responsiveness:** The willingness to help customers and to provide prompt service

Service Quality Method

The Gap Model and Gap Analysis

The research and the service quality methods will shed light to the service provider's perspective since currently this area is largely unexplored. This statement is strengthened by Svensson (2004) who states that the existing models of service quality are frequently based on the interpretations of involving different actors in a service encounter but not the service provider's point of view. This model is developed by Parasuraman et al. (1985). It proposed that that service quality is a function of the differences between expectation and performance along the quality dimensions.

Review of Literature

Yuning Wang, Zhe Zhang, Mengyuan Zhu, and Hexian Wang (2020) concludes that Quality of service has a significant impact on customer satisfaction and service quality, and customer satisfaction has an impact on travelers' reuse thinking. Service quality can be conceived as a

combination of the four dimensions of operational service quality, technical service quality, comfort and cleanliness and service planning and reliability.

Bikramjit Singh Hundal and Vikas Kumar (2015) in their study the researchers suggests that timely management of trains and training of railway staff should be highly responsive to the need and demand of passengers. Safety measurements should be improved so that passengers feel safe while traveling. In other words, the missing human contact is much needed in the Northern Railway passenger services. The improvement of these features will help improve service quality gaps and ultimately improve the competitiveness of Indian Railways.

Sheeba and Kumuthadevi (2013) the researchers suggests that extensive effort to implement qualified services for customers. Implement an effective and remote service quality model. Focus on important service quality factors such as basic amenities, health and safety-safety, which are considered to be the most important factors for train passengers. Railways should pay more attention to provide such services as basic amenities and hygiene are important factors to determine customer satisfaction. The designed satisfaction model can be upgraded or modified, Qualified services and overall satisfaction for passengers on the train.

According to **Devi Prasad Maruvada and Raja Shekhar Bellamkonda (2010)** Creates an analytics framework that contains a vague measure of the S -I (satisfaction - importance) degree. The measurement of the S-I gap with the Fuzzy approach is to reduce the subjectivity and ambiguity of the passenger service quality judgment. Fuzzy logic helps to indicate the ambiguity of the evaluators' judgment. Using the SERVQAUL method, the optimal ambiguous interval of interval scores is determined for each object. The researcher indicates that a lot of work needs to be done by the Railway administration to achieve passenger satisfaction by improving service quality.

The previous studies explained five dimensions of service quality but this study explained eight dimensions of service Quality.

Methodology of the Study

The main objective of the study is to analyse the gap between passengers expectations and perceptions. Primary data were collected by interviewing **100** passengers of Rail transport in

Southern Railway with a specially prepared interview schedule. The data were analysed by using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) software package. The researcher has applied Simple Percentage analysis, Gap analysis, Factor analysis and Correlation analysis.

Results and Discussion

Demographic profile of the respondents

The study shows that out of 100 respondents, 10 percent of the respondents are male the remaining 90 percent of the respondents are female. In age group, just one percent of the respondents are below 20 years, 20-40 years (97%), and 40-60 years (2%), married (21%), 4 percentage of the respondents are having the qualification of Higher Secondary or School, Diploma (1%), Under Graduation (22%), Post Graduation (71%), and others (2%). With regards to the Monthly Income 40 percentage of the respondents has Below Rs. 10000, between Rs. 10000 and Rs. 20000 (45%), between Rs. 20000 and Rs. 30000 (6%), and Above Rs. 30000 (9%). Further it is known from the study that 74 percent of the respondents are students, Professionals (5%), proprietor (1%), Business persons (3%), and others (17%). Hence, the study discloses that the female respondents availed most of the services than the male respondents and most of the respondents 97 percent are middle aged people, and are unmarried and are well qualified.

Gap analysis for the Service Quality Measures

This model is developed by Parasuraman et al. (1985). It proposed that that service quality is a function of the differences between expectation and performance along the quality dimensions.

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.958	58

Source: Derived

The data reliability has been tested by using the statistic Cronbach alpha. The Cronbach's Alpha comes up to be .958. As per the standards, the value needs to be greater than 0.5. Hence it can be concluded that the data is adequate.

Table 2 GapanalysisbetweenExpectationsandPerceptions

Variables	Expectations	Perceptions	Gap(E-P)	%ofSatisfactio
Itiseasytofinddetailsregardingtrainschedule	4.08	3.93	0.15	96.32
Punctualityoftrainservices	3.86	3.69	0.17	95.59
Itiseasytofind/detailsregardingtrainfare	3.92	3.66	0.26	93.37
Passengersfeelthatgovernmentsupportsallcategoriesofpeople	4.15	3.57	0.58	86.02
Railwaysupportssomesectionofpublicwithtravelconcessions	4.18	3.48	0.70	83.25
Railwaystaffarereliable	3.88	3.48	0.40	89.69
Updatedinformationaboutstatusoftrainduringtravel	4.34	3.53	0.81	81.34
Itiseasytobookaticketintrain	4.31	3.53	0.78	81.90
ComplaintHandlingSystemsResponsiveness	4.46	3.4	1.06	76.23
Availabilityofstaffinhandlingrequests(Dependabilityin handling your service problems)	4.39	3.26	1.13	74.26
Trainticketsareavailableeasily	4.34	3.99	0.35	91.94
Travellingbytrainsavestraveltime	4.24	3.51	0.73	82.78
Itissafetotravelintrain	4.40	3.95	0.45	89.77
Passengersprefertrainjourneybeforeoptingothertravelmodes through road or air	4.15	3.76	0.39	90.60
Providingyouwithinformationaboutanychangersinternary	4.23	3.62	0.61	85.58
Informationregardingsafetyproceduresarereadilyavailable	4.24	3.50	0.74	82.55
Trainreservationandcancellationprocessissimple	4.30	3.51	0.79	81.63
Staffattheticketoffice	4.42	3.51	0.91	79.41
Securitypersonnelareeasilyapproachable	4.62	3.56	1.06	77.06
Sufficientspaceandfacilitiesareinthetrainforpassengers	4.6	3.41	1.19	74.13
FacilitiesavailableinRailwaystationissufficient	4.63	3.53	1.10	76.24
Thegoodthingabouttrainjourneyisit'scomfort	4.37	4.03	0.34	92.22
Passengersfeelrelaxedinatrainjourney	4.28	3.76	0.52	87.85
Railwayshelppublicinlongdistancetravel	4.26	3.56	0.73	83.57

Ticketreservationsystemprovidesequalopportunitiestoall passengers	4.65	3.55	1.10	76.34
Medicalfacilityinthetrain	4.61	3.49	1.12	75.70
Foodfacilityinthetrain	4.2	3.23	0.97	76.90
Sufficientinformationisavailable regardingtrainschedule	4.58	3.46	1.12	75.55
Cleanlinessoftrain	4.28	3.32	0.96	77.57
Modernappearanceofstation	4.22	3.21	1.01	76.07
Cleanlinessofthestation	4.61	3.24	1.37	70.28
Traintimetablesprovideenoughinformationtoplanajourney	4.54	3.4	1.14	74.89
Trainreservationsystemisuserfriendly	4.6	3.85	0.75	83.70
Railwayshasagoodimageamongpublic	4.48	3.66	0.82	81.70
Railwaysaretrustworthy meansoftransport	4.33	3.51	0.82	81.06
Easyandaccessiblecomplainthandlingmechanismisinplace	4.35	3.5	0.85	80.46
Assistanceandinformationfordisabledandelderlypeopleis good	4.27	3.57	0.70	83.61
Concessionfordisabledandelderlypeopleis good	4.29	3.52	0.77	82.05
Concessionforstudentsandchildrenisgood	4.61	3.58	1.03	77.66
AvailabilityofCarriers(Coolieandtrolley)	4.59	3.56	1.03	77.56
Railwaystreatpassengerswithutmostrespect	4.27	3.67	0.60	85.95
Railwaystaffareapproachable	4.53	3.93	0.60	86.75
Railwaystaffprovidesufficientinformationwhenaskedfor details	4.28	3.48	0.80	81.31
Theserviceintrainisexcellent	4.61	3.64	0.97	78.96
Informationregardingchangeintraindetailsaregivenproactively	4.55	3.33	1.22	73.19
Availabilityofseatingintrain	4.3	3.94	0.36	91.63
Comfortableseatsinthetrain	4.54	3.68	0.86	81.06
Comfortabletemperatureinthetrain	4.24	3.65	0.59	86.08
Smoothnessofrideofthetrain	4.52	3.63	0.89	80.31
Travellingtimeofthetrain	4.26	3.49	0.77	81.92
Adequacyofparkingfacilities	4.59	3.85	0.74	83.88
Easeofaccesstoyourhomestation	4.28	3.68	0.60	85.98
Easeofaccesstotheneareststationatyourworkingplace	4.64	3.62	1.02	78.02

Frequencyoftrainsthatmeetyourneeds	4.38	3.39	0.99	77.40
Trainsrunningatsuitabletimesforcatchingconnectingtransport	4.63	3.47	1.16	74.95
Easeofaccessoftravelinformation	4.3	3.9	0.40	90.70
Easeofbuyingtickets	4.63	3.56	1.07	76.89
Convenientofficehoursatticketoffice	4.61	3.51	1.10	76.14

Source:PrimarySurvey

The above table shows that Expectations and Perceptions of the respondents regarding different attributes like It is easy to find details regarding train schedule, Punctuality of train services, It is easy to find/ details regarding train fare, Passengers feel that government supports all categories of people and so on. Here the gap between Expectations and Perceptions has been calculated and percentage of satisfaction of different respondent regarding the above said attributes has also been calculated.

Table3PercentageofsatisfactionintheServiceQualityDimensions

Dimensions	Expectations	Perceptions	Gap(E-P)	%of Satisfaction
Reliability	4.18	3.59	0.59	85.89
Assurance	4.40	3.59	0.80	81.59
Tangibility	4.42	3.48	0.94	78.73
Empathy	4.44	3.59	0.85	80.86
Responsiveness	4.45	3.61	0.84	81.12
Comfort	4.37	3.68	0.69	84.21
Connection	4.50	3.60	0.90	80.00
Convenience	4.51	3.73	0.86	82.71
Correlation	0.21			
AverageGapScore			0.81	82.00

Source:PrimarySurvey

The Gap score is more for the dimensions tangibility and Convenience and is low for Reliability and comfort. The correlation between the scores of Expectations and Perceptions is low to the extent of 0.21 whereas the average gap score is 0.81 and the percentage of overall

satisfaction is turned to be 82 percent. Hence it is noted that the percentage of satisfaction level is high among the sample respondents.

Chart 1 Percentage of satisfaction in the Service Quality Dimensions

Average Mean has been calculated for analysis of gap for the various dimensions namely Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy, Responsiveness, Comfort, Connection and Convenience. For the present analysis, eight dimensions considered and it has been observed that Reliability dimension has lesser gap which involving it is easy to find details regarding train schedule, Punctuality of train services, It is easy to find/ details regarding train fare, Passengers feel that government supports all categories of people, Railways supports some section of public with travel concessions, Railway staff are reliable. The major gap has been found in Tangibility which involving The good thing about train journey is it's comfort, Passengers feel relaxed in a train journey, Railways help public in long distance travel, Ticket reservation system provides equal opportunities to all passengers, Medical facility in the train, Food facility in the train, Sufficient information is available regarding train schedule, Cleanliness of train, Modern appearance of station, Cleanliness of the station and Train time tables provide enough information to plan a journey.

Perception of the passenger towards Service Quality Measures

Perception of the passengers in the study area is discussed in this section, by applying Factor Analysis. **Factor Analysis** is a good way of resolving the confusion and identifying important variables. The technique of factor analysis is used to reduce the number of variables into smaller and manageable number combining related ones into factors. **Principal Component Analysis** method is used to extract factors in Eigen value of one or more. In order to assign variables **Rotated Factor Matrix** is used. In order to find out the appropriateness of this analysis Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are used and the results are shown below.

Table 4 Reliability Statistics

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.755
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4388.064
	Df	1653
	Sig.	.000

Source: Derived

Normally KMO is between 0 and 1, if KMO is 0.5, the sample is adequate. Here, KMO = 0.755 which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the Factor Analysis. The KMO value is very high (0.755). Similarly, the Bartlett's Test rejects the null hypothesis, i.e, the variables are not related as the approximate chi-square value is 4388.064 at 1653 degrees of freedom which is significant at 5 percent. Thus factor analysis may be considered as an appropriate technique.

Table 5 Perception of the passenger towards Service Quality Measures

Perception	Infrastructure	Convenience	Performance	Hygienic
Sufficient space and facilities are in the train for passengers	.691	.118	.105	.113
Staff at the ticket office	.682	.118	.229	.248
Availability of Carriers (Coolie and trolley)	.681	.084	.018	.205
Concession for disabled and elderly people is good	.633	.245	-.042	.239
Passengers feel that government supports all categories of people	.604	.044	.050	.274
Passengers prefer train journey before opting other travel modes through road or air	.577	.223	.325	-.062
Punctuality of train services	.562	.245	.189	.022
Information regarding safety procedures are readily available	.562	.335	.327	.101
Smoothness of ride of the train	.556	.220	.136	.296
Passengers feel relaxed in a train journey	.484	.200	.106	.030
Railway has a good image among public	.482	.161	.276	.250
Sufficient information is available regarding train schedule	.482	.132	.263	.366
Medical facility in the train	.410	.198	.377	.177
It is easy to find/details regarding train fare	.409	.380	.388	-.080
Railway supports some section of public with travel concessions	.409	.092	.263	.314
Ticket reservations system provides equal opportunities to all passengers	.405	.269	.366	.349
Railway staff are reliable	.183	.657	.025	.212
Travelling time of the train	.391	.630	-.154	.073
Ease of access to your home station	.269	.600	.085	.107
Ease of buying tickets	.345	.590	.277	.151

Concessionforstudentsandchildrenisgood	-.060	.579	.343	.321
FacilitiesavailableinRailwaystationissufficient	.075	.578	.125	.112
Securitypersonnelareeasilyapproachable	.123	.567	.343	.316
Comfortabletemperatureinthetrain	.061	.565	.206	.054
Itiseasytobookaticketintrain	.368	.551	.120	.207
Railwaystaffprovidesufficientinformationwhenaskedfor details	-.038	.518	.048	.380
Travellingbytrainsavestraveltime	.433	.512	.250	.095
Railwayshelppublicinlongdistancetravel	.299	.509	.109	-.043
Availabilityofstaffinhandlingrequests(Dependabilityin handlingyourserviceproblems)	.143	.491	.174	.347
Informationregardingchangeintraindetailsaregivenproactively	.228	.471	-.279	.411
Trainreservationandcancellationprocessissimple	.086	.448	.325	.326
Thegoodthingabouttrainjourneyisit'scomfort	.044	.391	.228	.004
Railwaysaretrustworthymeansoftransport	.351	.383	.254	-.066
Trainticketsareavailableeasily	.036	.208	.767	.094
Trainreservationsystemisuserfriendly	.119	.167	.706	.147
Easeofaccessoftravelinformation	.245	.274	.627	.022
Availabilityofseatingintrain	-.001	.338	.613	.229
Itiseasytofinddetailsregardingtrainschedule	.287	.223	.607	.030
Itissafetotravelintrain	.181	.026	.607	-.043
Railwaystaffareapproachable	.160	-.063	.606	.404
Adequacyofparkingfacilities	.339	.347	.531	.030
Railwaystreatpassengerswithutmostrespect	.029	.195	.503	.279
ComplaintHandlingSystemsResponsiveness	.430	-.137	.433	.340
Updatedinformationaboutstatusoftrainduringtravel	.395	.019	.408	.316
Theserviceintrainisexcellent	.359	.037	.392	.351
Assistanceandinformationfordisabledandelderlypeopleisgood	.286	.266	.310	.265

Foodfacilityinthetrain	-.172	.268	.237	.609
Cleanlinessoftrain	.061	.161	.124	.606
Easeofaccesstothenearreststationatyourworkingplace	.271	.199	-.137	.579
Convenientofficehoursatticketoffice	.416	.076	.135	.579
Trainsrunningatsuitabletimesforcatchingconnectingtransport	.431	.056	.050	.553
Cleanlinessofthestation	.171	-.112	.332	.539
Comfortableseatsinthetrain	.312	.286	.134	.511
Easyandaccessiblecomplainthandlingmechanismisinplace	.428	.294	-.024	.466
Traintimetablesprovideenoughinformationtoplanajourney	.361	.396	.048	.421
Providingwithinformationaboutanychangersinternary	.282	.219	.244	.388
Frequencyoftrainsthatmeettheneeds	.224	.248	.116	.335
Modernappearanceofstation	.273	.254	.181	.323
Eigenvalue	17.54	3.33	3.044	2.49
PercentVariation	30.24	5.74	5.248	4.29
CumulativePercent	30.24	35.98	41.23	45.5

Source:PrimarySurvey

The above table clearly shows that in the first column the variables namely Sufficient space and facilities are in the train for passengers, Staffat the ticketoffice and so on have higher holdings.691, .682,.681, .633..604, .577,.562, .562,.556., 484,.482, .482,.410, .409,.409 and .405 respectively and it is suggested that factor 1 is the combination of sixteen factors and have the variance 30.24 and it can be termed as Service Factor. From the second column it can be seen that the variables of Railway staff are reliable, Travelling time of the train and so on have holdings.657,.630,.600,.590,.579,.578,.567,.565,.551,.518,.512,.509,.491,.471,.448, .391 and .383 respectively and it is suggested that Factor 2 is the combination of these seventeen factors and have the variance of 5.74 percent and it can be termed as Convenience Factor.

The third column shows that the variables of Train tickets are available easily, Train reservationsystemisuserfriendlyandsoonhaveholdings.767,.706,.627,.613,.607,.607,

.606, .531, .503, .433, .408, .392 and .310 respectively and it is suggested that Factor 3 is the combination of these thirteen factors and have the variance of 5.248 percent and it can be termed as Performance Factor. The fourth column shows that the factors that Food facility in the train, Cleanliness of train, Ease of access to the nearest station at your working place and the like have loadings .609, .606, .579, .579, .553, .539, .511, .466, .421, .388, .335, .323 and it is suggested that Factor 4 is the combination of these twelve factors and have the variance of 4.29 percent and it can be termed as Hygienic Factor. Thus the 58 variables are reduced into 4 factors and are given different names by using factor analysis, accordingly Infrastructure Factor, Convenience Factor, Performance Factor and Hygienic Factor have been identified as the Perception of the employees.

Conclusion

The study discloses that the female respondents availed most of the services than the male respondents and most of the respondents 97 percent are 20-40 aged people, most of the respondents are unmarried. The survey reveals that most of the respondents (71%) are Post Graduates and most of the respondents (45%) are have Rs.10000-Rs. 20000 and most of the respondents are student. For the present analysis, Reliability, Assurance, Tangibility, Empathy, Responsiveness, Convenient, Comfort, Connection dimensions, the Gap score is more for the dimensions tangibility and Convenience and is low for Reliability and comfort. The 58 variables are reduced into 4 factors and are given different names by using factor analysis accordingly Infrastructure Factor, Convenience Factor, Performance Factor and Hygienic Factor have been identified as the Perception of the employees. Hence it is suggested that it is utmost under the purview of the Southern Railway to take great concern and care in the implementation of proper hygiene to retain the rail passengers with full satisfaction.

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